

The effect of dietary fish oil replacement by microalgae on the gilthead sea bream midgut bacterial microbiota

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Table S1. PERMANOVA pairwise test for alpha diversity metrics based on Bray – Curtis distance matrix. Statistically significant differences for $p < 0.05$ are shown in red. FO: Fish Oil, PI: *Phaeodactylum* + *Isochrysis*, SP: *Schizochytrium* + *Phaeodactylum*, MI: *Microchloropsis* + *Isochrysis*.

Taxa_S				
Aquafeed	FO	PI	SP	MI
FO	-	0.636	0.411	0.106
PI		-	0.342	0.046
SP			-	0.718
MI				-

Chao-1				
Aquafeed	FO	PI	SP	MI
FO	-	0.429	0.547	0.220
PI		-	0.562	0.442
SP			-	0.623
MI				-

Shannon-H				
Aquafeed	FO	PI	SP	MI
FO	-	0.911	0.470	0.124
PI		-	0.286	0.049
SP			-	0.529
MI				-

Simpson 1-D				
Aquafeed	FO	PI	SP	MI
FO	-	0.940	0.412	0.164
PI		-	0.388	0.112
SP			-	0.632
MI				-

Table S2. PERMANOVA pairwise test for all samples based on Bray – Curtis distance matrix. Statistically significant differences for $p < 0.05$ are shown in red. FO: Fish Oil, PI: *Phaeodactylum* + *Isochrysis*, SP: *Schizochytrium* + *Phaeodactylum*, MI: *Microchloropsis* + *Isochrysis*.

Aquafeed	FO	PI	SP	MI
FO	-	0.034	0.817	0.790
PI		-	0.024	0.089
SP			-	0.851
MI				-

Table S3. Most abundant OTUs in each feeding group. FO: Fish Oil, MI: *Microchloropsis* + *Isochrysis*, SP: *Schizochytrium* + *Phaeodactylum*, PI: *Phaeodactylum* + *Isochrysis*.

Aquafeed	Relative Abundance of the most abundant OTU (% of reads), closest relative (>97%)	No. of dominant OTUs with $\geq 80\%$ cumulative relative abundance
FO	OTU-0001 (27.6%), <i>Mycolicibacterium aurum</i>	17
MI	OTU-0001 (28.3%), <i>Mycolicibacterium aurum</i>	10
SP	OTU-0001 (27.1%), <i>Mycolicibacterium aurum</i>	14
PI	OTU-0004 (23.9%), <i>Yoonia litorea</i>	12

Table S4. Taxonomy and closest relative of the OTUs with the GenBank accession numbers (Nucleotide BLAST) depicted in Figure 7. FO: Fish Oil, MI: *Microchloropsis* + *Isochrysis*, SP: *Schizochytrium* + *Phaeodactylum*, PI: *Phaeodactylum* + *Isochrysis*.

FO high abundance OTUs compared to the three experimental feed groups			
11 common OTUs in FO-PI, FO-MI and FO-SP			
OTU010	Proteobacteria	Rhizobiaceae	<i>Hoeflea halophila</i> (100.00%) - MT628728.1
OTU020	Proteobacteria	Rhizobiaceae	<i>Brucella melitensis</i> (99.25%) - MT611105.1
OTU026	Proteobacteria	Burkholderiales_unclassified	<i>Ralstonia insidiosa</i> (99.53%) - MK968569.1
OTU044	Proteobacteria	Rhizobiaceae	<i>Aquamicrobium</i> sp. (98.26%) - MT457451.1
OTU045	Proteobacteria	Coxiellaceae	<i>Coxiella-like endosymbiont</i> (96.04%) - MH645185.1
OTU047	Proteobacteria	Caulobacteraceae	<i>Brevundimonas</i> sp. (100.00%) - MN620407.1
OTU050	Proteobacteria	Rhizobiaceae	<i>Mesorhizobium albisiae</i> (100.00%) - KP337606.1
OTU056	Acidobacteriota	Blastocatellaceae	uncultured <i>Firmicutes bacterium</i> (100.00%) - EU298762.1
OTU065	Bacteroidota	Weeksellaceae	<i>Cloacibacterium normanense</i> (100.00%) - MK294295.1
OTU070	Bacteroidota	Weeksellaceae	<i>Chryseobacterium</i> sp. (100.00%) - CP050993.1
OTU077	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteriota_unclassified	uncultured <i>Actinobacterium</i> (97.66%) - JN178908.1
2 common OTUs in FO-PI and FO-MI			
OTU016	Firmicutes	Streptococcaceae	uncultured <i>Streptococcus</i> sp. (100.00%) - LT681499.1
OTU018	Firmicutes	Clostridiaceae	Uncultured <i>clostridium</i> sp. (99.75%) - MN663533.1
1 common OTU in FO-PI and FO-SP			
OTU030	Proteobacteria	Xanthobacteraceae	<i>Rhodopseudomonas</i> sp. (100.00%) - MN555639.1
1 common OTU in FO-MI and FO-SP			
OTU008	Proteobacteria	Rhodobacteraceae	<i>Marivita litorea</i> (99.25%) - MN746209.1
1 OTU included exclusively in FO-SP			

OTU004	Proteobacteria	Rhodobacteraceae	<i>Yoonia litorea</i> (99.25%) - MZ443920.1
Common high abundance OTUs of FO with MI, PI and SP			
2 common OTUs in FO-PI, FO-MI and FO-SP			
OTU001	Actinobacteriota	Mycobacteriaceae	<i>Mycolic bacterium aurum</i> (99.26%) - MT406679.1
OTU003	Firmicutes	Staphylococcaceae	uncultured <i>Staphylococcus</i> sp. (99.77%) - FJ957685.1
2 common OTUs in FO-PI and FO-MI			
OTU004	Proteobacteria	Rhodobacteraceae	<i>Yoonia litorea</i> (99.25%) - MZ443920.1
OTU012	Actinobacteriota	Propionibacteriaceae	<i>Cutibacterium acnes</i> (100.00%) - MT613579.1
1 OTU included exclusively in FO-PI			
OTU008	Proteobacteria	Rhodobacteraceae	<i>Marivita litorea</i> (99.25%) - MN746209.1
1 OTU included exclusively in FO-MI			
OTU030	Proteobacteria	Xanthobacteraceae	<i>Rhodopseudomonas</i> sp. (100.00%) - MN555639.1
3 OTUs included exclusively in FO-SP			
OTU016	Firmicutes	Streptococcaceae	uncultured <i>Streptococcus</i> sp. (100.00%) - LT681499.1
OTU018	Firmicutes	Clostridiaceae	Uncultured <i>clostridium</i> sp. (99.75%) - MN663533.1
OTU023	Proteobacteria	Sphingomonadaceae	<i>Sphingorhabdus</i> sp. (99.75%) - MK493524.1
MI, PI and SP high abundance OTUs compared to FO			
2 common OTUs in FO-PI and FO-MI			
OTU006	Proteobacteria	Vibrionaceae	<i>Vibrio</i> sp. (99.53%) - KY914442.1
OTU027	Proteobacteria	Vibrionaceae	<i>Vibrio</i> sp. (99.77%) - MT634723.1
7 OTUs included exclusively in FO-PI			
OTU005	Proteobacteria	Vibrionaceae	<i>Vibrio</i> sp. (99.30%) - MN252252.1
OTU011	Verrucomicrobiota	Chlamydiales_unclassified	uncultured <i>Candidatus</i> <i>protochlamydia</i> sp. (91.82%) - OP914912.1
OTU022	Proteobacteria	Devosiaceae	<i>Devosia mishustinii</i> (98.49%) - KX982774.1
OTU034	Bacteroidota	Flavobacteriaceae	<i>Polaribacter aquimarinus</i> (100.00%) - OP344420.1
OTU038	Proteobacteria	Moraxellaceae	<i>Psychrobacter sanguinis</i> (99.30%) - MN758810.1
OTU039	Firmicutes	Bacillaceae	<i>Anoxybacillus</i> sp. (100.00%) - MN885758.1
OTU076	Proteobacteria	Rhodobacteraceae	<i>Planktotalea</i> sp. (99.75%) - KP172216.1
7 OTUs included exclusively in FO-MI			

OTU007	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteria_unclassified	uncultured <i>Corynebacterium</i> sp. (99.76%) - LT692791.1
OTU009	Firmicutes	Clostridia_unclassified	<i>Candidatus arthromitus</i> sp. (98.01%) - AP012210.1
OTU013	Proteobacteria	Pseudoalteromonadaceae	<i>Pseudoalteromonas</i> sp. (99.53%) - MF975560.1
OTU015	Proteobacteria	Vibrionaceae	<i>Vibrio chagasii</i> (99.30%) - MT269630.1
OTU031	Proteobacteria	Pseudomonadaceae	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. (99.30%) - MT585910.1
OTU037	Verrucomicrobiota	Chlamydiales_unclassified	Uncultured <i>Chlamydiales</i> bacterium (96.96%) - KC902452.1
OTU041	Proteobacteria	Comamonadaceae	uncultured <i>Bacillus</i> sp. (99.53%) - EU567044.2
11 OTUs included exclusively in FO-SP			
OTU002	Bacteroidota	Bacteroidia_unclassified	uncultured <i>Flavobacteriales</i> bacterium (91.51%) - FJ425622.1
OTU012	Actinobacteriota	Propionibacteriaceae	<i>Cutibacterium acnes</i> (100.00%) - MT613579.1
OTU014	Proteobacteria	Moraxellaceae	<i>Acinetobacter Iwoffii</i> (99.77%) - MT626722.1
OTU021	Verrucomicrobiota	Simkaniaceae	uncultured <i>Chlamydiae</i> bacterium (91.59%) - DQ996921.1
OTU025	Proteobacteria	Beijerinckiaceae	<i>Methylobacterium</i> sp. (99.25%) - LC546537.1
OTU028	Actinobacteriota	Corynebacteriaceae	uncultured <i>Actinomycetales</i> bacterium (99.26%) - HM076482.1
OTU033	Proteobacteria	Pseudomonadaceae	<i>Halopseudomonas formosensis</i> (99.06%) - MT313134.1
OTU042	Proteobacteria	Pasteurellaceae	uncultured <i>Haemophilus</i> sp. (100.00%) - ON786180.1
OTU048	Proteobacteria	Oxalobacteraceae	<i>Massilia timonae</i> (100.00%) - MN932364.1
OTU068	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae	<i>Blautia</i> sp. Marseille-P3313 (97.26%) - LT631509.1
OTU069	Actinobacteriota	Actinobacteriota_unclassified	Uncultured <i>Solirubrobacterales</i> bacterium (100.00%) - JQ401013.1

Table S5. Overexpressed and underexpressed Pathways (from Metacyc database) in PI, MI and SP compared to FO. FO: Fish Oil, MI: *Microchloropsis* + *Isochrysis*, SP: *Schizochytrium* + *Phaeodactylum*, PI: *Phaeodactylum* + *Isochrysis*.

Overexpressed pathways in MI, PI, SP compared to FO	
1 common Pathway in PI/FO, MI/FO and SP/FO	
FUCCAT-PWY	Degradation → L-Fucose Degradation
6 common Pathways in PI/FO and MI/FO	
PWY-7446	Carbohydrate Degradation → Sulfoquinovose Degradation
PWY0-1338	Lipopolysaccharide Biosynthesis
PWY-6906	Carbohydrate Degradation → Sugar → Chitin
P162-PWY	Proteinogenic Amino Acid Degradation → L-glutamate Degradation
PWY-6565	Amide, Amidine, Amine, and Polyamine Biosynthesis
PWY-5177	Carboxylic Acid Degradation
3 common Pathways in MI/FO and SP/FO	
PWY-6749	Sugar Biosynthesis → Sugar → sialic acids
P163-PWY	Proteinogenic Amino Acid Degradation → L-glutamate Degradation
PWY-7456	Carbohydrate Degradation → Polysaccharide Degradation → plant mannan degradation
1 common Pathway in PI/FO and SP/FO	
P621-PWY	caprolactam degradation
Underexpressed Pathways in MI, PI, SP compared to FO	
1 common Pathway in PI/FO, MI/FO and SP/FO	
PWY-6470	Cell Wall Biosynthesis → Peptidoglycan Biosynthesis
1 Pathway included exclusively in PI/FO	
PWY-7295	Sugar Degradation → L-arabinose Degradation
2 Pathways included exclusively in MI/FO	
PWY-6992	Sugar Degradation → anhydrofructose pathway
VALDEG-PWY	Proteinogenic Amino Acid Degradation → L-valine Degradation
1 Pathway included exclusively in SP/FO	
RHAMCAT-PWY	Sugar Degradation → L-rhamnose Degradation

Table S6. The genus-level OTUs that contain all the enzymes of L-fucose degradation (from the KEGG database). Numbers indicate KEGG enzyme codes. + = it contains the enzyme, - = it does not contain the enzyme. Numbers indicate enzyme code.

OTUs	Genus	L-fucose mutarotase [5.1.3.29]	L-fucose isomerase [5.3.1.25]	L-fuculokinase [2.7.1.51]	L-fuculose-phosphate aldolase [4.1.2.17]
OTU001	<i>Mycolicibacterium</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU003	<i>Staphylococcus</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU004	<i>Yoonia</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU012	<i>Cutibacterium</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU008	<i>Marivita</i>	-	-	-	-
OTU030	<i>Rhodopseudomonas</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU016	<i>Streptococcus</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU018	<i>Clostridium</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU023	<i>Sphingorhabdus</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU005, 006, 027	<i>Vibrio</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU011	<i>Candidatus</i> Protochlamydia	+	+	+	+
OTU022	<i>Devosia</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU034	<i>Polaribacter</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU038	<i>Psychrobacter</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU039	<i>Anoxybacillus</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU076	<i>Planktotalea</i>	-	-	-	-
OTU007	<i>Corynebacterium</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU009	<i>Candidatus</i> Arthromitus	+	+	+	+
OTU013	<i>Pseudoalteromonas</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU031	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU041	<i>Bacillus</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU012	<i>Cutibacterium</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU014	<i>Acinetobacter</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU025	<i>Methylobacterium</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU033	<i>Halopseudomonas</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU042	<i>Haemophilus</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU048	<i>Massilia</i>	+	+	+	+
OTU068	<i>Blautia</i>	+	+	+	+

Table S7. Overexpressed SP pathways and OTUs with the higher taxon function abundance in each metabolic pathway. OTUs unique in the SP treatment are depicted with *

PWY-3941 - β-alanine biosynthesis II	Abundance
OTU001	41.02
OTU019	24.78
OTU036	20.26
OTU010	13.51
OTU029	10.84
PWY-5677-succinate fermentation to butanoate	
OTU014	201.74
OTU010	63.80
OTU036	47.76
OTU018	28.43
PWY-6944-androstenedione degradation I (aerobic)	
OTU001	3972.25
OTU036	824.84
OTU019	302.69
OTU010	220.15
OTU029	132.34
PWY-7527-L-methionine salvage cycle III	
OTU001	19.97
OTU002	19.67
OTU025	9.64
PWY-922 - mevalonate pathway I (eukaryotes and bacteria)	
OTU001	819.79
OTU016	810.29
*OTU069	171.64
OTU036	148.06
OTU025	137.70
OTU010	111.16
PYRIDOXYN-PWY - pyridoxal 5'-phosphate biosynthesis I	
OTU014	4203.82
OTU001	3123.00
OTU017	1349.27
OTU019	1078.93
OTU036	881.17
SUCSYN-PWY - sucrose biosynthesis I (from photosynthesis)	
OTU001	820.66
OTU025	573.00
OTU042	466.80
OTU017	397.23
OTU028	342.05
TEICHOICACID-PWY - poly(glycerol phosphate) wall teichoic acid biosynthesis	
OTU001	8.33
OTU017	2.15
OTU002	1.84

Figure S1. (a) Venn diagram demonstrating the number of common and unique OTUs and their percentages in the four feeding groups (FO, PI, SP, MI). **(b)** Venn diagrams demonstrating the numbers and percentages of the unique and common OTUs between the three experimental feed groups (MI, PI, SP) and the control (FO). FO: Fish Oil, MI: *Microchloropsis* + *Isochrysis*, SP: *Schizochytrium* + *Phaeodactylum*, PI: *Phaeodactylum* + *Isochrysis*.

Figure S2. Relative Abundance ratio of the three most dominant phyla in each feeding group. Relative abundances were calculated from the average sample reads of each OTU. FO: Fish Oil, MI: *Microchloropsis* + *Isochrysis*, SP: *Schizochytrium* + *Phaeodactylum*, PI: *Phaeodactylum* + *Isochrysis*.